

DESCRIPTION AND CHARACTERISTICS OF HIGH SILICON ZEOLITIC SYSTEMS FROM LOCAL RAW MATERIALS

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Abstract. *In this article, the issues of chemical and physical activation of kaolin and bentonite, which are natural local raw materials, and the textural characteristics and surface morphology of the obtained high-silica zeolites were studied. The influence of the method of activation of kaolin and bentonite on its colloidal and sorption capacity was investigated. As a result of the research, the heat of wetting, the amount of adsorbed bound water and the effective specific surface area were determined experimentally.*

Keywords: *zeolite, kaolin, bentonite, surface, sorption capacity, adsorption bound water, porosity, heat of wetting.*

INTRODUCTION

Separation processes are of extremely high importance for our society, comprising 10–15% of the global energy use and 40–90% of the total process cost. On one hand, most of the existing chemical processes do not yield products with the desired purity, directly suitable for further use. This is the case of petrochemical products or alcohols produced by fermentation, both of which require purification steps after being produced. On the other hand, the separation and purification of naturally occurring mixtures, such as air or natural gas, is of high environmental, economical, and/or practical interest.

Due to its unique properties, zeolites are used in various fields of production, and their annual turnover in the world market is several million tons. Zeolites are increasingly used in gas petrochemistry, ion exchange (water purification and softening), adsorption and separation of vapors and gases, and removal of impurities from gases and solutions (especially harmful and environmentally hazardous). In addition, zeolites are more widely used in agriculture, animal husbandry, paper industry and construction. Zeolites have the ability to act as catalysts of various chemical reactions, which take place either inside the cavities or at the mouths of the pores of their pore-channel structure. An important class of reactions are those catalyzed by hydrogen-exchanged (or simply hydrogenated) forms of zeolites, whose backbone-bound protons are highly acidic. This property is used in most organic reactions, including crude oil cracking, hydrocarbon isomerization, and fuel synthesis. In the chemical industry, adsorption methods are the most common in the purification of hydrocarbons from various impurities and sulfur compounds, and the use of these methods allows the return of a number of valuable compounds to production. The most important requirements for adsorbent materials are: having a high specific surface area, selectivity and easy regeneration [1-3]. Also, the adsorbent should be cheap and harmless, not have corrosive properties, be able to maintain its adsorption properties for a long time, and have high mechanical precision. One of the most common adsorbents is activated carbon, which is produced in different brands. In recent years, natural and artificial zeolites have been widely used in the treatment of hydrocarbon raw materials. Currently, one of the most important topical directions is the creation of environmentally safe sorbents, retainers and catalysts based on local raw materials [4-6].

Experience

To determine the chemical and physical-chemical characteristics of natural zeolites, we placed 100 g of sample granules in a 250 cm³ glass flask and added 150 cm³ of distilled water. The flask was stirred for 24 h in an AVU-6 device at 120 rpm. After drying, the adsorbent was passed through a sieve of 0.5 and 0.25 mm, and the mechanical and physical properties of the samples that passed through the sieve of 0.5 mm and remained on the sieve of 0.25 mm chemical characteristics were studied. Before acid treatment, the soils were ground to a size of 0.08 mm. We added 40 ml of heated H₂SO₄ to 10 g of ground soil and heated with stirring in a water bath. After the treatment, the soil was filtered with a paper filter in a Buchner funnel and washed in distilled water in the range of pH=5.4-5.7. Then the soil was dried together with the filter paper at 120°C for 5 hours in a drying cabinet. The distribution of pores in terms of surface area and size was determined by the method of low-temperature desorption of nitrogen in the automatic adsorbometer "ASAB 2010". Sedimentation analysis was carried out according to Oden's method in different dispersion mediums in water and water-glycerol mixture.

Heterogeneous systems are characterized by the size of their crystallites. This is due to the fact that the smaller the size of the crystallites are, the greater their surface area is, which leads to an increase in the activity of catalytic systems in the process of accelerating chemical reactions.

The property of accelerating chemical reactions of heterogeneous systems is determined by the relative surface area, the size of pores, and the distribution of micro-, meso-, and macropores. The relative surface-to-surface and pore size distribution in YUKS was determined by the low-temperature nitrogen adsorption method. The relative surface area was calculated by the BET (Brunauer-EmmetTeller) method, and the pore size distribution was calculated by the BJH (Barrett-JounerHaland) method.

Experimental results and their discussion

The main process in soil activation is the replacement of divalent ions (Ca⁺² and Mg⁺²) with monovalent alkali metals. The main purpose of the work is to choose optimal conditions for activation of alkaline earth metal bentonites. Processing of alkaline earth metal bentonites was carried out under different conditions. The reagent for the experiment is 0.1 in relation to the total mass of the sample; it was added in amounts of 0.2 and 5%. In order to evaluate the results of the activation, the physical and chemical characteristics of the material, such as its colloidal properties and its resistance to swelling, were determined. The efficiency of ion exchange was evaluated by the amount of calcium and magnesium cations exchanged in the mineral after activation. As can be seen from the figure below, when 0.1% Na₂CO₃ is added to the starting material, the colloidability of bentonite powders increases dramatically. When the amount of the reagent increases to 2 and 5%, the colloidal property does not increase, but decreases.

Table 1

Sorption capacities of modified and unmodified bentonite

Indicator	Indicator size			
	Bentonite		Modification	
	Natural	enriched	with H ₂ SO ₄	with Na ₂ CO ₃
Sorption capacity, mg-ekv/100	72,6	75,0	38,7	119,1

The water absorption indicator was observed during activation with 2% soda, this indicator decreases as the amount of the reagent increases.

One of the thermodynamic parameters characterizing the adsorption properties of the adsorbent was calculated as its heat of wetting:

$$\Delta H_{\text{wet}} = S_{\text{comp}} \cdot (E_1 - E_2)$$

In this case, S_{comp} is the relative surface area of the adsorbent, E_1 is the total surface energy of the adsorbent at the air interphase boundary; E_2 is the total surface energy at the adsorbent-liquid interface.

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The amount of adsorption-bound water was calculated using the following formula:

$$A = (\Delta H_{\text{wet}} \cdot r \cdot h / q) \cdot 100$$

In this ΔH_{wet} -heat of wetting of 1 g of soil, J/g; r -density of adsorption water; $r=1.2-1.3 \cdot 10^6$ g/m³; q -wetting of 1 m² of soil surface heat does not depend on powder dispersion, $q=0.116$ j/m²; h -water layer thickness, $h \approx 2.7 \cdot 10^{-10}$ m.

The effective surface area of the soil was calculated according to the following formula:

$$S_{\text{comp (effect)}} = \Delta H_{\text{wet}} / q, \text{ m}^2 / \text{g}$$

Table 2

Soil sorption characteristics

Appearance of the material under examination	Heat of wetting, J/g	Amount of adsorbed bound water, A, % by mass	Effective specific surface area, m m ² /g
Kaolin-water	9,38	5,78	149,2
Bentonite-water	37,8	15,75	315,5

Calculations show that kaolin has the minimum effective surface area, bentonite has the maximum value, which gives insight into their structure.

The amount of heat released during adsorption is determined calorimetrically.

CONCLUSION

1. Local raw materials: kaolin and bentonite were activated by chemical and physical methods, and the textural characteristics and surface morphology of the obtained high-silica zeolites were studied.

2. The influence of the method of activation of kaolin and bentonite on its colloidal and sorption capacity was investigated. As a result of the research, the heat of wetting, the amount of adsorbed bound water and the effective specific surface area were determined experimentally.

3. The water absorption indicator was observed during activation with 2% soda, this indicator decreases as the amount of the reagent increases.

4. One of the thermodynamic parameters characterizing the adsorption properties of the adsorbent was calculated as its heat of wetting.

5. As a result of the research, it was proved that the effective comparative surface area of kaolin is minimal, and that of bentonite is maximal.

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